

Shrine at Horvat Qitmit

By Andrew Danielson, University of British Columbia

Entry tags: Levantine Religion, Religious Place, Religious Group, Religious Complex, Shrine, Open-Air Sanctuary, Canaanite Religions, Syro-Palestinian Religion

The site of Horvat Qitmit is located in the semi-arid Beersheba-Arad valley of the northeastern Negev in the southern Levant. Dating from the 8th through the early 6th century BCE, this site was located within the southern geographic range of influence of the Kingdom of Judah to the north, based at Jerusalem. Nonetheless, the majority of the material culture from Horvat Qitmit shows strong parallels and similarity to that excavated in southern Transjordan, in the Kingdom of Edom. For this reason, Horvat Qitmit has often been called an “Edomite” shrine. In fact, recent research has demonstrated the cultural diversity of this northeastern Negev region that was located along a major east-west trade corridor that connected the Mediterranean Sea to Judah, Edom, and Arabia to the southeast. Due to these trade connections as well as the mobile agropastoral subsistence nature of the region, the “Edomite” material culture at Horvat Qitmit in fact represents persons established within, and local to the region. In addition to travelers and other mobile groups, this “Edomite” subset of the local populace frequented this shrine for generations. The primary deity worshipped at Horvat Qitmit was likely the deity Qos (𐤒𐤓), as is attested in the inscriptions at the site. Qos is primarily known at this time as the foremost deity of Edom. There is evidence for at least one additional deity, a goddess (Astarte or Asherah?) attested in statuary, who may have been understood as the consort of the weather-type deity Qos. The site was eventually abandoned in the late 7th or more likely early 6th century BCE, at a time contemporary to the settlement collapse of this region that was in large part associated with the imperial Neo-Babylonian invasions of the southern Levant.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 586 BCE

Region: Horvat Qitmit Shrine

Region tags: Levant, Israel, Palestine, Negev, Judah

The shrine of Horvat Qitmit in the Beersheba-Arad Valley of the northeastern Negev.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Beit-Arieh, Itzhaq. 1995. *Horvat Qitmit: An Edomite Shrine in the Biblical Negev*. Monograph Series 11. Tel Aviv: Institute of Archaeology, Tel Aviv University.

— Source 2: Beck, Pirhiya. 1995. “Catalogue of Cult Objects and Study of the Iconography.” Pages 27-197 in *Horvat Qitmit: An Edomite Shrine in the Biblical Negev*. Edited by Itzhaq Beit-Arieh. Monograph Series 11. Tel Aviv: Institute of Archaeology, Tel Aviv University.

— Source 3: Beck, Pirhiya. 1996. “Horvat Qitmit Revisited via ‘En Hazeva.” *Tel Aviv* 23: 102-14.

Notes: See also: Finkelstein, Israel. 1992. "Ḥorvat Qitmit and the Southern Trade in the Late Iron Age II." *Zeitschrift Des Deutschen Palästina-Vereins* 108 (2): 156-70. Porter, Benjamin. 2004. "Authority, Polity and Tenuous Elites in Iron Age Edom (Jordan)." *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 23 (4): 373-95. Danielson, A. 2020. *Edom in Judah: An Archaeological Investigation of Identity, Interaction, and Social Entanglement in the Negev During the Late Iron Age (8th-6th Centuries BCE)* (Ph.D. dissertation, University of California at Los Angeles). Los Angeles. Danielson, A. 2021. "Culinary Traditions in the Borderlands of Judah and Edom during the Late Iron Age." *Tel Aviv* 48: 87-111.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.imj.org.il/en/placee/horvat-qitmit>

– Source 1 Description: Israel Museum holdings of artifacts from Horvat Qitmit

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1984-1986

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Horvat Qitmit, Institute of Archaeology of Tel Aviv University

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Type of feature

–Other [specify]: Enclosures

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Type of feature

– Clearing

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: There are a number of towns and forts within a 5-10 km radius, but there are no settlements in the immediate vicinity of Horvat Qitmit. The nearest substantive town is Tel Malhata, located 5 km to the northwest.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of towns and forts within a 5-10 km radius, but there are no settlements in the immediate vicinity of Horvat Qitmit. The nearest substantive town is Tel Malhata, located 5 km to the northwest.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Horvat Qitmit sits in the Beersheba-Arad Valley that served as a major corridor for east-west movement through the region, and also as a corridor for trade with Arabia. Finkelstein, Israel. 1992. "Horvat Qiṭmīt and the Southern Trade in the Late Iron Age II." *Zeitschrift Des Deutschen Palästina-Vereins* 108 (2): 156-70.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: There are a number of towns and forts within a 5-10 km radius, but there are no settlements in the immediate vicinity of Horvat Qitmit. The nearest substantive town is Tel Malhata, located 5 km to the northwest.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ A single structure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: It appears that both Complex A and Complex B were built contemporaneously. Both were likewise renovated (Beit-Arieh 1995: 9-26).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Adjacent Complex A and Complex B are two stone enclosures.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

– Sacrificial

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

– Social

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Notes: It appears that both Complex A and Complex B were built contemporaneously. Both were likewise renovated (Beit-Arieh 1995: 9-26).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Qos was likely the primary deity.

Notes: See Beck 1995: 188-189.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Evidence of at least a female deity is also present, perhaps Astarte or Asherah (Beck 1995: 188-189).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of construction of Horvat Qitmit is not fully understood. It served the local inhabitants of the Beersheba-Arad Valley region of the northeastern Negev, as well as likely travelers through the region, many coming from the southeast: Edom and Arabia. The similarities in the material culture between Horvat Qitmit and the Kingdom of Edom to the east has led to suggestions of an Edomite political aspect to the site, though such a situation cannot be determined with complete certainty on the basis of the material culture finds. See discussion in: Danielson, A. 2020. *Edom in Judah: An Archaeological Investigation of Identity, Interaction, and Social Entanglement in the Negev During the Late Iron Age (8th–6th Centuries BCE)* (Ph.D. dissertation, University of California at Los Angeles). Los Angeles. Finkelstein, Israel. 1992. "Ḥorvat Qitmit and the Southern Trade in the Late Iron Age II." *Zeitschrift Des Deutschen Palästina-Vereins* 108 (2): 156–70. Porter, Benjamin. 2004. "Authority, Polity and Tenuous Elites in Iron Age Edom (Jordan)." *Oxford Journal of Archaeology* 23 (4): 373–95.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Notes: Though Complex A preserves a greater number of ritual material.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Earth

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Sand

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Clay

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Wood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Construction these buildings generally used wood, though this information is not recorded in the publication.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Notes: Construction these buildings generally used wood, though this information is not recorded in the publication. Unknown where the wood came from, but presumably was locally sourced.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ **Stone**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ **Is this material sourced locally:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ **Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ **Other**

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ **Is decoration part of the building (permanent):**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: See Beck (1996, 1996).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Sphinx (Beck 1995: 152-153).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Numerous figurines and statuary that have been interpreted as priests and worshippers (Beck 1995, 1996).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Bulls (associated often with storm gods), ibex, dog and numerous fragments of unidentified quadrupeds. Also present are numerous ostriches, a rooster, bird of prey and other birds. See Beck (1995; 1996).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Sphinx (Beck 1995: 152-153).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: An altar bears geographic motifs (Beit-Arieh 1995: 274-276), and the ceramic corpus presents numerous examples of denticulated fringes (Freud and Beit-Arieh 1995: 209-257). Freud, Liora, and Itzhaq Beit-Arieh. 1995. "Pottery." In *Horvat Qitmit: An Edomite Shrine in the Biblical Negev*, edited by Itzhaq Beit-Arieh, 209-57. Monograph Series 11. Tel Aviv: Tel Aviv University.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Pomegranates are present as decorations on chalices and bowls (Beck 1995: 156-159).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Engraved inscriptions are present on objects (offerings?) at the site (Beit-Arieh 1995: 258-268).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Likely priests of worshippers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Animal figurines are also present.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: Reliefs for clay models.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that some of the figures attached in relief to the stands represent deities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Human headed Sphinx (Beck 1995: 152-153). Other zoomorphic elements are present, though it is unclear/unlikely that they are intended to be supernatural.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Numerous figurines and statuary were excavated in a style that has commonly been associated with southern Transjordan and the Kingdom of Edom (Beck 1995; 1996).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Human narratives

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Based on the available inscriptional data, and circumstantial evidence, it may be somewhat confidently posited that Qos (as a weather god) was a major divinity of focus at Horvat Qitmit, together with at least one other female (consort?) deity (likely Astarte or Asherah) (Beck 1995: 188-189).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Qos would have most likely functioned as a weather deity/divine warrior (Danielson 2020: 116)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data. Qos was not "physically" related to elites, though we may presume that would have acted on behalf of the deity claiming to be agents of the divine.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ostensibly, yes, in abstract ways (based on regional comparisons).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: Fragments of statues were excavated (Beck 1995: 188-189), indicating that such statues were present.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the cult statue hidden:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient data

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The gods would certainly be honored and sacrificed to. The degree to which there was "communication" may be debated. The sacrifices were likely intended toward appeasement and/or supplication for the gods.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Beit-Arieh interprets the rituals as: sacrificial slaughter, cooking and feasting, ceremonial processions, music, placing offerings and burning incense, and prayer (Beit-Arieh 1995: 307-

308).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Beit-Arieh interprets the rituals as: sacrificial slaughter, cooking and feasting, ceremonial processions, music, placing offerings and burning incense, and prayer (Beit-Arieh 1995: 307-308).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown, on the basis of the size of the space and the material culture finds, the number could be several dozens.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Unknown

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: An incense altar was excavated at the site. While residue analysis has not been performed on this particular object, studies of contemporaneous other exemplars from this region preserved evidence of frankincense and cannabis (Arie et al. 2020) among other possible intoxicants. Likewise, alcohol in the form of wine, is prominent in the region, and likely attested at the site by bowls and cups, as a part of larger feasts. Arie, E., Rosen, B., and D. Namdar. 2020. "Cannabis and Frankincense at the Judahite Shrine of Arad." *Tel Aviv*: 47:5-28.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Sheep/Goat with lesser numbers of Cattle are preserved.

Notes: The faunal remains present at the site include: Complex A Sheep/Goat: 91% (MNI 5) Cattle: 9% (MNI 1) Complex B Sheep/Goat: 94% (MNI 7) Cattle: 6% (MNI 2) Horwitz, Liora Kolska, and Ora Raphael. 1995. "Faunal Remains." In *Horvat Qitmit: An Edomite Shrine in the Biblical Negev*, edited by Itzhaq Beit-Arieh, 287-302. Tel Aviv: Sonia and Marco Nadler Institute of Archaeology, Tel Aviv University.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Metal (Bronze and Iron) objects were excavated amidst a variety of ceramic, stone, and shell objects.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Some objects are, others appear to be more specific to particular rituals at the site

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: Beit-Arieh notes the discovery of a large accumulation of pottery and objects near a cliff approximately 70 m southeast of the site, that he interprets as a possible favissa (Beit-Arieh 1995: 13).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Ritual specific objects: figurines, statuary, ceramic body parts were also

encountered.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: Beit Ariesh notes that the deposition of finds suggests periodic cleaning, and perhaps the use of a favissa (Beit-Arieh 1995: 12-13).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: Both Complex A and Complex B were renovated (Beit-Arieh 1995: 9-26).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: The southern portion of Complex A.

Notes: See discussion in Danielson (2020: 204-205). Danielson, A. 2020. Edom in Judah: An Archaeological Investigation of Identity, Interaction, and Social Entanglement in the Negev During the Late Iron Age (8th-6th Centuries BCE) (Ph.D. dissertation, University of California at Los Angeles). Los Angeles.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably yes, though there is no direct evidence of such.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is probable that divination was practiced, though direct evidence is lacking.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that healing was practiced. A large number of ceramic body parts (that could be associated with healing) were excavated at the site, though it is clear that many come from larger statues and figurines.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Beit-Arieh interprets several of the rooms as being the living quarters of priests (1995: 308).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: The nature of the finds within the site suggest close cultural ties to southern Transjordan and the Kingdom of Edom. Though "Edomite" as an "ethnicity" needs careful qualification (Danielson 2020), culturally this site is more closely aligned with southern Transjordan than the region of southern Judah in which it is located. Danielson, A. 2020. Edom in Judah: An Archaeological Investigation of Identity, Interaction, and Social Entanglement in the Negev During the Late Iron Age (8th–6th Centuries BCE) (Ph.D. dissertation, University of California at Los Angeles). Los Angeles.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If priests are present, they were likely of a higher status than the regular population.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Beit-Arieh interprets several of the rooms as being the living quarters of priests (1995: 308).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: There are several pottery vessels that bear engraved inscriptions on them, suggesting they were dedications of some sort presented to the shrine. (The engraved inscriptions stand in contrast to the common practice of ink on pottery).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Horvat Qitmit

Bibliography

General References

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